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A Secure Distributed Database System Using Rijndael Encryption Algorithm

MFON, Idorenyin Edet

Department of Computer Science, Akwa Ibom State Polytechnic, Ikot Osurua

Phone: 07016914633 (WhatsApp Number) or 07069421578

Email: iddymfon4real@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In today's interconnected world, secure storage and management of data are critical concerns for organizations dealing with sensitive information. With the advent of distributed computing and the need for collaborative work environments, the demand for secure distributed database systems has grown significantly. There is a pressing need to secure distributed database system in order to effectively address some challenges such as no encryption of users' access details in the database which could be hacked by skilled hands, and so on. This research aims at developing a secure distributed database system using the Rijndael encryption algorithm also known as the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES). By leveraging the robust cryptographic features of Rijndael, we strive to create a secure and efficient distributed database system that ensures the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of data in a distributed environment. In this project, both primary and secondary sources of data were employed and Rapid Application Development (RAD) was adopted as system development methodology. The proposed system employed an approach that uses Secured Harsh Algorithm (SHA-3) for encrypting login details of users, Rijndael algorithm to encrypt and re-encrypt text and image data in order to improve the security strength and make it difficult for unauthorized personnel to have access to data stored in the database. This system was implemented on Windows 10 platform with Visual Basic.Net as programming language, and SQLite as relational database. The result of this proposed system showed that it has the capability of capturing the user's details for registration and encrypting the user's password with SHA-3 algorithm. The user can send encrypted text and/or image data with less amount of time and can also receive encrypted data, decrypt it without any

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change in quality of the data. The research concludes that with this system, it is impossible for intruders to gain access to the application or compromise the security of the text or image data and users can share (send and receive) sensitive data/information in a secured manner without any interception.

Keywords: Secured, Database, Encryption, Organizations.

INTRODUCTION

Distributed databases (DDBs) are groups of related databases that are located in various parts of the world but are linked together digitally via a system of servers. In a distributed database, data may be read from, processed, and written to several locations at once, all without the user seeing a difference. DDBs are useful because they facilitate the storage and processing of certain types of data, including audio, video, and text (Toapanta et al., 2020).

Nonetheless, as the number of apps that use connected distributed databases grows, so does the amount of data produced by these applications, thereby raising serious concerns about the privacy and safety of this information (Toapanta et al., 2020). A data security system or protection of information from unwanted access, alteration, abuse, or destruction, is essential for any distributed database as stated by Karthick (2018). In a distributed database, data security refers to the measures taken to prevent unauthorised users or harmful software from gaining access to the database. Ensuring services like confidentiality, authentication, dependability, integrity, and elastic scalability in databases has long been one of the primary security problems impacting users in a distributed environment (Ferretti, Colajanni, & Marchetti, 2014).

Toapanta et al. (2020) state that cryptographic methods, biometric methodology, genetic algorithms, quick response code mechanisms, steganography, watermark, and data integrity algorithms are necessary to mitigate against attacks or increase the levels of security in a distributed database.

Cryptography is employed to protect the data. The goal of cryptography, as defined by Gupta and Sharma (2013), is to ensure that only the intended receiver is able to decrypt a message provided in an encrypted form, securing communication in the presence of eavesdroppers is the domain of cryptography. Using encryption methods,

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data may be transformed into unintelligible cypher text. This method is used to ensure the privacy of sensitive information during transmission. Encryption methods like Data Encryption Standard (DES), Rivest Cipher (RC4), Advanced Encryption Standard based on Rijndael Algorithm, Triple DES (3DES), and so on are used to convert a plain text database into a (partially) encrypted database, rendering the original unreadable to anyone who does not have access to the corresponding encryption key(s) (Bouganim & Guo, 2013). The Rijndael algorithm is a block cypher that has become the *de facto* industry standard due to its efficiency, effectiveness, and ease of implementation. It allows for a wider variety of block and key sizes to be used.

Traditional centralized database systems face limitations in terms of scalability, fault tolerance, and data access speed. In addition, as sensitive data becomes a prime target for cyber-attacks, organizations struggle to safeguard their databases from unauthorized access and data breaches. In a distributed environment, where data is stored across multiple nodes, the complexity of ensuring data security and privacy increases significantly. Hence, there is a pressing need to develop a secure distributed database system that can effectively address these challenges.

This study explores the use of encryption algorithms like Rijndael and Secure Hash Algorithm (SHA-3) to safeguard text and picture data in a distributed database against intrusion and malicious assaults at the storage, database, and application levels.

RELATED WORKS

Research efforts in recent years have concentrated on finding ways to improve DDB systems' efficiency. Protection of databases in the encrypted realm was addressed by Xiang, Ruan, Li, and He (2021), who presented an order-preserving encryption system (OPES) using circular histograms and digital watermarking technology. Information stored in the cloud was encrypted using OPES to prevent unauthorised access. The encrypted information was then clustered and altered with the use of a circular histogram to insert a digital watermark. For the encrypted watermarking database, several database query operations were employed so that, upon reception, both the digital watermark and the original data could be recovered using a secret key and a key table.

It was suggested by Guclu, Bakir, and Hakkoymaz (2020) that an access control

mechanism be used to increase the safety of DDB systems. When determining a user's permission level, this access control policy took into account the user's identification and the security dimension. Because the rules were static and the access control was dependent on a single, ineffective measure, more malevolent users were able to bypass the system's defences.

Sawiris and Abdel-Fattah (2020) presented a revolutionary approach to distributed databases by proposing deep learning-based fragmentation and allocation as well as blockchain technology-based security provisioning. In this case, the system was utilised to guarantee the most efficient realisation of the recommended answer.

Data semantic fragmentation was presented by Amer, Sewisy, and Elgendy (2017), who suggested a method that use a common clustering technique. The system also presented a novel approach to query management in remote databases, using intelligent query processing. This approach facilitated the distribution of workloads.

METHODOLOGY

The proposed system is a database security system for handling user access authentication and data encryption. It is a software application capable of securing and managing text and image data in a distributed database at storage, database, and application levels in order to protect the system against unauthorized access, hackers, and attacks through encryption algorithms such as Secured Hash Algorithm (SHA-3) and Rijndael algorithm of Advanced Encryption Standard (AES).

a. Proposed Methodology

The proposed system would take the steps below in actualizing the development of the application. However, the application encrypts data and stores it into the database as well as decrypting the stored-encrypted data.

1. Acquire text or image data: This phase takes care of data acquisition in form of text or image. The user can enter text data or upload image data into the application.
2. Convert to Byte: This phase takes care of the conversion of text or image data into 64-byte data.

3. Encrypt Data: This phase takes care of encrypting the text or image data that was converted into byte. After the encryption process is done, the first key is produced or generated.
4. Re-encrypt data: In order to increase the security of the data and the database, at this phase, the encrypted text or image data is re-encrypted and the second key is generated.
5. Display encrypted data: This phase handles the display of encrypted text or image data as well as the storage of the encrypted data.
6. Retrieve Data: This phase handles the retrieval of stored data from the database and calls “get-keys” phase to get the keys and prepare for decryption process.
7. Decrypt Data: This phase handles the decryption of text or image data retrieved from the database.
8. Re-decrypt Data: This phase handles the re-decryption of text or image data, which was already decrypted.
9. Convert 64 byte to data: At this phase, the re-decrypted data, which is in byte form, is converted into text or image data.
10. Display data: This phase displays the text or image data that has been decrypted.

b. Proposed System model

Rapid Application Development (RAD) is another approach used in the creation of this system. Using this strategy, you can be certain that you'll have a high-quality system that will serve your customers well for the long haul. There are four stages of development in this process, and they are: requirement planning, user design, construction, and cutover. Secured Harsh Algorithm (SHA-3) is used to encrypt user login information, while the Rijndael algorithm is used to encrypt and re-encrypt text and picture data. This is done to increase security and make it more difficult for unauthorised individuals to access the data contained in the database. DotNET framework and the SQLite database would be used, while Windows 10 operating system and Visual Basic would power this system's development.

Users' increased engagement throughout the development process is a primary reason why RAD has gained popularity. Involvement of the user in the project from its earliest stages of design to execution allows for necessary adjustments to be made to the encryption system. The money, time, and energy it saves is immeasurable. This is because all changes were tracked and implemented throughout the encryption's development, making the project less stressful and more efficient. It enables fast modifications to the system's architecture in response to user feedback; allows for human input and development at the early stage.

c. The Functional Model of the Proposed System

The Unified Modelling Language (UML) Use Case diagram for proposed system is shown in Figure 1. The Use Case diagram illustrates how the users interact with the system. It also describes the graphic diction of the interaction among the element of the system and the methodology used in system analysis to clarify and organize system requirement. It shows how functionalities relate between the internal/external actors.

The following are actors and the participants of the system:

Actors: User (Sender and Receiver)

User (Sender and receiver): The users get registered, login, send data, view profile, receive data and log out.

Figure1: Use case diagram of the proposed system

d. Activity Diagram of the Proposed System

The activity diagram illustrates the behavior of the proposed system with regards to various activities. These activities are modeling elements that depict the execution of a set of operations. However, the execution of these activities can be triggered by the completion of other activities by the availability of objects, or by internal/external events. Figure 2 shows different activities for the proposed system, with rounded rectangles representing activities; arrows between activities representing control flow and thick bars representing the synchronization of control flow.

Figure2: User Activity Diagram of the proposed System

e. Architecture of the Proposed System

The illustrative representation of the proposed system architecture is shown in figure 3 below. System architecture depicts the various key components of the proposed system. The user sends text and/or picture data to where the data is encrypted and re-encrypted with Rijndael algorithm, generates keys and stored to distributed database. The user receives the text/image data after the data has been decrypted and [re-decrypted and the keys entered]. The data is stored into MySQL database.

Figure3: System Architecture of the proposed system

Encrypt: This phase gets the text/image data from the user, encrypts it and generates the first key; it also re-encrypts already encrypted data, generates the second key and then stores the keys and data into the database.

Keys: This phase is keys manager that maintains the keys generated from the “encrypt” phase and it is stored into the database. During the “decrypt” process, the keys are sent to the “decrypt” phase, where they are used for the decryption of the text or image data.

Decrypt: This phase gets the encrypted data retrieved from the database, gets the keys

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from the key manager, decrypts and re-decrypts the data, and then displays the original data to the user.

Database: This phase stores the text and image data - the keys and users' data. The credential data is encrypted with SHA-3 algorithm and textual and image data are also encrypted and stored with Rijndael algorithm. This is MySQL database.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Based on the result of the proposed system, figure 4 shows the system's capability of capturing the user's details for registration, encrypting the user's password with SHA-3 algorithm and saving it into the database. Figure 5 shows how the system captures the user's details for login and if the details are correct, user is given access to the application. With SHA-3 function, no key is required, but rather a fixed length hash value is computed on the basis of the user's password. It allows for checks of password integrity to ensure that the user's password has not been altered, compromised or affected by virus.

Figure 4: Register user screen

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LOGIN USER

Username idmfon

Password #####

Login Close

Figure5: Login user screen

In figure 6 below, the system allows the user to send data as encrypted text and/or image by selecting the kind of data type to send (text, image or both text and image data). After the selection, the user can then enter texts data and/or upload image data, while the system converts the text and/or image data into 64-byte and encrypts it. After the encryption process is done, the first key is produced or generated and the encrypted text or image data is re-encrypted and the second key is generated. Then the encrypted text or image data is displayed and stored. In this process, two keys are generated and the encrypted data is sent to the receiver. Different sizes of text data and image data have been encrypted using Rijndael algorithm, the result of the implementation of Rijndael algorithm showed that the user can use less amount of time to enter required data (text and/or image) to encrypt and send.

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Figure 6: Send Data (Encrypted Data) screen

After the receiver's session identity number has been entered, the system retrieves the stored data from the database and calls “get-keys” phase to get the keys and prepare for decryption process. The decryption of text or image data retrieved from the data base starts when the user clicks on the decryption button and the decrypted data is re-decrypted, and the system converts the 64-byte data to original data, thereafter, displays the original text and/or image data. The system also revealed that the quality of the image did not change during the process of encrypting and re-encrypting the image data as well as when the image was decrypted and re-decrypted. Figure 7 shows how a receiver gets the session identity number, logs into the application to retrieve the encrypted data.

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Figure7: Receive Data (Retrieved Data) screen

However, in figure 8, the system allowed the glistered user to view their displayed information under user profile.

Figure8: User Profile screen

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Generally, the result also demonstrated the fact that due to the encryption of users' access details in the data base, it was impossible for intruders to gain access to the application, and the security of the text or image data was not compromised because re-encrypting the data helped to enhance the security of data. Being a distributed system, the users were able to share (send and receive) data/information in a secured manner without any interception. However, this system is observed to be cost effective and also saved time.

CONCLUSION

As science and technology advances with positive outcomes for human development, there is need for improved security system to ensure the safety of data transfer between devices, especially through the internet. As this research has shown, this fear of insecurity has been curbed by the use of our proposed system. The result shows that the security of users' access to application was enhanced through the use of Secure Hash Algorithm (SHA-3) by encrypting users' access details in the database, thereby, thwarting intruders' effort in gaining access to the database as those details were stored in an unreadable format.

The issues about the use of some algorithms with weak or semi-weak keys and encryption of only textual data was circumvented with the use of Rijndael algorithm encrypt, re-encrypt data in a distributed database as well as decrypt and re-decrypt of this data. Being a distributed system, the system hindered interception and manipulation of data while improved data integrity and confidentiality.

With this approach, users can now use very little time to enter required data (text and/or image) to encrypt without any deterioration in the quality of the image during the process of encryption and decryption. The system ensures that the security of the data is not compromised because re-encrypting the data helps to enhance its security and this system is strongly recommended to organizations and institutions like schools, banks, and other bodies dealing with sensitive and confidential information because its double encrypting and decrypting processes promise absolute security of data. It is cost effective and also saves time.

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